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**Improvement of the economic mechanism of distance learning of specialists in
tourism in higher educational institutions as the prerequisite of territorial
development ensuring**

*Abstract. The economic mechanism of distance learning of specialists in
tourism in higher educational institutions in the context of ensuring territorial
development is improved in the article. This mechanism is based on economic
assessment of risks of distance learning of specialists in tourism. The general*

assessment of positive and negative characteristics of distance learning in the whole showed that the positive ones are the following: lowering of expenses of education; transformation of the advanced techniques of training on the periphery; development of skills of independent work among students; an opportunity to involve results of the most professional teachers in interactive educational process and improvement of quality of monitoring of knowledge due to detail study of test jobs and problems setting. But distance learning is connected with the following negative trends: lack of direct perception of material; lack of an opportunity for a discussion and lack of direct control over the implementation of tasks. The identification and evaluation of the risks of distance learning of specialists in tourism with the help of expert evaluations method showed that the opportunity to conclude that probable problems of technical character and imperfect control system of training results are characterized by the critical level of safety. The lack of skills of self-organization in the process of distance learning is in the precritical condition. As for the other risks – they are in the unstable condition. The complex of actions for increase of efficiency of distance learning of specialists in tourism in higher educational institutions based on the pedagogical technology is proposed. The given technology means dependence of quality of knowledge of students of distance learning on the level of motivational program and pedagogical communications.

Keywords: *economic mechanism; risks; distance learning; specialists in tourism; expert evaluations method; higher educational institutions; territorial development.*

Introduction. The tourism is a prerequisite of territorial development as the touristic sphere covers a set of elements of infrastructure of territories which, in turn is an integral part of economic space and provides activity of territories. For this reason training of qualified specialists in tourism is necessary in modern conditions. At the same time it should be noted that there is an active introduction of distance learning in educational process, including training of specialists in tourism in present conditions when information and communication technologies accompany all modern

fields of activity. The innovative standards of training are focused on system and activity approach which provides formation of students' ability to self-development and continuous education. And it is possible to realize the given prospects only by means of distance learning. The distance learning of specialists in tourism allows learning of new and perspective directions, such as the following: work with electronic booking systems, use of information logistics systems, development of systems of decision making support on development of business plans of tourist complexes and enterprises, etc. However distance learning of specialists in tourism is accompanied by a number of risks which can significantly complicate the training process and assessment of its effectiveness.

The analysis of research and problem definition. The questions devoted to the effective organization of distance learning in higher educational institutions were investigated by the following domestic and foreign authors: O. Peters, M. Moore, D. Keegan etc.

In particular, the scientist O. Peters suggested considering a phenomenon of distance learning from the point of view of the economic theory of industrialization [1]. The author M. Moore placed emphasis that the main condition of good results of training is the direct interpersonal contact of the teacher with students [2]. The researcher D. Keegan focused attention on those fact that the spatial dissociation provides division of processes of training and teaching [3].

However risks of distance learning in higher educational institutions, in particular, concerning training of specialists in tourism are insufficiently investigated.

Paper objective. The purpose of the article is improving of the economic mechanism of distance learning of specialists in tourism in higher educational institutions in the context of territorial development ensuring.

Accordingly, the following problems are solved in the work for achievement of the given purpose:

- General assessment of positive and negative characteristics of distance learning in the whole;

- Identification and evaluation of risks of distance learning of specialists in tourism;

- Development of the complex of actions for increase of efficiency of distance learning of specialists in tourism in higher educational institutions.

The results of the research. The analysis of results of earlier executed researches allows allocating the following invariants which need to be considered when developing program and methodical ensuring of distance learning in the sphere of tourism:

- Definition of the main requirements to different types of program and methodical providing;

- Choice of basic program systems and development environments of technologies of distance learning, educational and methodical materials and electronic educational and methodical complexes;

- Solution of the methodical questions connected with computer realization of training materials;

- Ensuring of protection of the software product against unauthorized access;

- Copyright compliance of the developer of the training program [2; 3].

Considering the average level of resource (personnel and material) ensuring of the process of informatization of tourist specialties in most higher education institutions it is necessary to place emphasis on a combination of use of case and network technologies when developing an educational and methodical complex of distance learning. It provides a possibility of application of a remote educational and methodical complex irrespective of the level of informatization of educational process that, in turn, provides stability of distance learning system in the sphere of tourism [4].

Application of modular approach is the important feature of design of an electronic educational and methodical complex for “tourism” specialty. The modularity of an electronic educational and methodical complex provides structure openness, a possibility of addition and further extension of its contents and also big flexibility and variability of educational process.

However it is necessary to consider that these technologies have certain features (delivery of training materials, a way of knowledge certification, the testing mode, communication of teachers and students, management of educational process).

It is possible to mark the following ones among the positive moments of development of distant education: lowering of expenses of education; transformation of the advanced techniques of training on the periphery; development of skills of independent work among students; an opportunity to involve results of the most professional teachers in interactive educational process; improvement of quality of monitoring of knowledge due to detail study of test jobs and problems setting.

The distance learning has one key essential shortcoming at all its pluses – it doesn't assume direct contact between the teacher and the student. The lack of contact, in turn, creates the following problems: lack of direct perception of material; lack of an opportunity for a discussion; lack of direct control over the implementation of tasks [5].

Of course, the advanced western techniques try to solve this problem through the institute of distance tutoring when the personal teacher is attached to each student getting distance learning in the on-line mode. Existence of this condition solves a problem of dispassionateness of the student from educational process, and the lack of real-life verbal communication is replaced with high extent of personalization of communication between the teacher and the student. It should be noted that tutoring is actually not widespread in Ukraine even when receiving traditional education.

The sphere of distance learning is formed for a number of years. The terms framework and standard legal support are made out together with practice of creation of systems of distance learning. In this context a number of problem areas are allocated [6].

It is necessary to decide on, first of all, the concept of education according to which the training purposes are defined and the content is formed in distance learning. The training purposes and content are defined in the existing standard of education and in the program. They are obligatory for all forms of education within the basic education.

The situation is a little different in additional education. Extension of the content of education is the first problem area. The personally focused approach assumes independent cognitive activity of students connected with cognitive and communication skills.

Availability and expansibility of an educational information resource is the second problem area. The educational environment which includes the distributed electronic libraries, the state, branch and corporate educational Internet resources, separate multimedia training materials, plays an important role in providing of students with training materials. Development of reference books and qualifiers of modern sign, schematic and other tools of the description and production of knowledge is the perspective direction of development of systems of distance learning [7; 8].

Development of a standard legal basis of distance learning is the third problem area.

Copyright compliance on elements of the educational environment and infrastructure is the fourth problem area. This area is especially allocated from the third area owing to its specifics [9– 11].

Proceeding from the aforesaid, it should be noted that introduction of distance learning is always connected with a set of risks. Accordingly, it is offered to carry out the analysis of these risks by means of method of expert evaluations in the work.

At first, several experts need to be selected for research carrying out. They not necessarily should be specialists in an investigated question. Usually their quantity makes 5–7 persons.

It is offered to choose the following persons as experts for the current evaluation: the teacher on animation tourism; the logistics specialist of the transport enterprise; the tourism manager; the guide on the international tourism; the head of the hotel and restaurant complex.

Secondary, a number of the analyzed risks should be selected. For example, these risks can be the following ones: lack of skills of self-organization in the process of distance learning; insufficient motivation; restrictions on time; problems of

technical character; absence of the software satisfying personal students' need; imperfect control system of training results; difficulties of information security ensuring.

Thirdly, the experts evaluate competence of each other by the scale from 0 to 1. The results of their evaluation are given in table 1.

4. Fourthly, an average competence of each expert is calculated as arithmetic-mean size.

In particular, the average competence of the teacher on animation tourism is calculated in such a way:

$$\overline{K}_1 = \frac{0.87 + 0.77 + 0.95 + 0.84 + 0.74}{5} = \frac{4.17}{5} = 0.83.$$

The average competence of the tourism manager is calculated in such a way:

$$\overline{K}_2 = \frac{0.79 + 0.86 + 0.78 + 0.82 + 0.84}{5} = \frac{4.09}{5} = 0.82.$$

The average competence of the teacher on animation tourism is calculated as follows:

$$\overline{K}_3 = \frac{0.91 + 0.94 + 0.94 + 0.75 + 0.96}{5} = \frac{4.5}{5} = 0.90.$$

Tab. 1: The progress of evaluation of the competences of the experts

№	Expert	Competence coefficients				
		The teacher on animation tourism	The logistics specialist of the transport enterprise	The tourism manager	The guide on the international tourism	The head of the hotel and restaurant complex
1	The teacher on animation tourism	0.87	0.79	0.91	0.69	0.73
2	The logistics specialist of the transport enterprise	0.77	0.86	0.94	0.83	0.78
3	The tourism manager	0.95	0.78	0.94	0.69	0.91
4	The guide on	0.84	0.82	0.75	0.97	0.79

	the international tourism					
5	The head of the hotel and restaurant complex	0.74	0.84	0.96	0.94	0.83

Source: compiled by the authors based on [5; 7]

The average competence of the guide on the international tourism is calculated in such a way:

$$\overline{K}_4 = \frac{0.73 + 0.78 + 0.91 + 0.79 + 0.83}{5} = \frac{4.04}{5} = 0.80.$$

The average competence of the head of the hotel and restaurant complex is calculated as follows:

$$\overline{K}_5 = \frac{0.91 + 0.94 + 0.94 + 0.75 + 0.96}{5} = \frac{4.5}{5} = 0.90.$$

The results of calculations of average competence of experts are shown in table 2.

Tab. 2: The average competences of the experts

The expert	The average competence
The teacher on animation tourism	0.83
The logistics specialist of the transport enterprise	0.82
The tourism manager	0.90
The guide on the international tourism	0.80
The head of a hotel and restaurant complex	0.90

Source: compiled by the authors based on [5; 7]

Fifthly, the experts evaluate the given risks by the scale from 0 to 1. The results are displayed in table 3.

Tab. 3: The evaluation of risks of distance learning by the experts

№	The risk	Expert
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		The teacher on animation tourism	The logistics specialist of the transport enterprise	The tourism manager	The guide on the international tourism	The head of the hotel and restaurant complex
1	Lack of skills of self-organization in the process of distance learning	0.93	0.89	0.95	0.91	0.88
2	Insufficient motivation	0.23	0.31	0.40	0.19	0.37
3	Restrictions on time	0.45	0.51	0.38	0.49	0.19
4	Problems of technical character	0.85	0.74	0.92	0.73	0.88
5	Absence of the software satisfying personal students' need	0.34	0.22	0.56	0.62	0.37
6	Imperfect control system of training results	0.89	0.94	0.85	0.78	0.82
7	Difficulties of information security ensuring	0.61	0.43	0.29	0.38	0.57

Source: compiled by the authors based on [5; 7]

Sixthly, the average evaluations of level of the given risks are calculated.

These values are defined as the average weighed arithmetic values.

In particular, the average evaluation of the level of lack of skills of self-organization in the process of distance learning is calculated as follows:

$$\overline{BC}_1 = \frac{0.93 \times 0.83 + 0.89 \times 0.82 + 0.95 \times 0.90 + 0.91 \times 0.80 + 0.88 \times 0.90}{4.25} = \frac{3.10}{4.25} = 0.73.$$

The average evaluation of the insufficient motivation is calculated as follows:

$$\overline{BC}_2 = \frac{0.23 \times 0.83 + 0.31 \times 0.82 + 0.40 \times 0.90 + 0.19 \times 0.80 + 0.37 \times 0.90}{4.25} = \frac{1.28}{4.25} = 0.30.$$

The average evaluation of the restrictions on time is calculated as follows:

$$\overline{BC}_3 = \frac{0.45 \times 0.83 + 0.51 \times 0.82 + 0.38 \times 0.90 + 0.49 \times 0.80 + 0.19 \times 0.90}{4.25} = \frac{1.69}{4.25} = 0.40.$$

The average evaluation of the problems of technical character is calculated as follows:

$$\overline{BC}_4 = \frac{0.85 \times 0.83 + 0.74 \times 0.82 + 0.92 \times 0.90 + 0.73 \times 0.80 + 0.88 \times 0.90}{4.25} = \frac{3.5}{4.25} = 0.82.$$

The average evaluation of absence of the software satisfying personal students' need is calculated as follows:

$$\overline{BC}_5 = \frac{0.34 \times 0.83 + 0.22 \times 0.82 + 0.56 \times 0.90 + 0.62 \times 0.80 + 0.37 \times 0.90}{4.25} = \frac{1.79}{4.25} = 0.42.$$

The average evaluation of the imperfect control system of training results is calculated as follows:

$$\overline{BC}_6 = \frac{0.89 \times 0.83 + 0.94 \times 0.82 + 0.85 \times 0.90 + 0.78 \times 0.80 + 0.82 \times 0.90}{4.25} = \frac{3.64}{4.25} = 0.86.$$

The average evaluation of the difficulties of information security ensuring is calculated as follows:

$$\overline{BC}_7 = \frac{0.61 \times 0.83 + 0.43 \times 0.82 + 0.29 \times 0.90 + 0.38 \times 0.80 + 0.57 \times 0.90}{4.25} = \frac{1.92}{4.25} = 0.45.$$

Seventhly, the evaluation of the criticality of risks according to the following scale is made (Table 4).

Tab. 4: The scale for evaluation of the criticality of risks

The average value of risk probability	The level of safety
$BC_i = 1$	Crisis condition
$0,75 < BC_i < 1$	Critical level of safety
$0,50 < BC_i < 0,75$	Precritical condition
$BC_i = 0,50$	Uncertainty situation
$0,25 < BC_i < 0,50$	Unstable condition
$0 < BC_i < 0,25$	Normal level of safety
$BC_i = 0$	Absolute safety

Source: compiled by the authors based on [5; 7]

The results of the evaluation of the criticality of the given risks are shown in table. 5.

Tab. 5: The identification of the level of safety of the risks of distance learning

The risk	The average value	The level of safety
Lack of skills of self-organization in the process of distance learning	0.73	Precritical condition
Insufficient motivation	0.30	Unstable condition
Restrictions on time	0.40	Unstable condition
Problems of technical character	0.82	Critical level of safety
Absence of the software satisfying personal students' need	0.42	Unstable condition
Imperfect control system of training results	0.86	Critical level of safety
Difficulties of information security ensuring	0.45	Unstable condition

Source: compiled by the authors based on [5; 7]

It is necessary to note in the context of the given results that probable problems of technical character and imperfect control system of training results are characterized by the critical level of safety. The lack of skills of self-organization in the process of distance learning is in the precritical condition. As for the other risks – they are in the unstable condition.

Accordingly, the development of pedagogical technology for training of specialists on tourism on the basis of higher educational institutions with the help of criteria system is offered in the work. This pedagogical technology should be based on establishment of dependence between the level of motivational program and target ensuring pedagogical communications and quality of knowledge of students of distance learning.

The given pedagogical technology will allow carrying out the following actions:

- Formation of educational motivation of independent work of students;

- Planning, organization and control of independent study of students on the basis of the qualimetric standards of process and at the end of it;
- Verification of effectiveness of educational and pedagogical activity during distance learning through regression communications and statistical processing.

Conclusion. Thus, during the research carrying out, the following results were received.

1. The general assessment of positive and negative characteristics of distance learning in the whole showed that the positive ones are the following: lowering of expenses of education; transformation of the advanced techniques of training on the periphery; development of skills of independent work among students; an opportunity to involve results of the most professional teachers in interactive educational process and improvement of quality of monitoring of knowledge due to detail study of test jobs and problems setting. But distance learning is connected with the following negative trends: lack of direct perception of material; lack of an opportunity for a discussion and lack of direct control over the implementation of tasks.

2. The identification and evaluation of the risks of distance learning of specialists in tourism gave the opportunity to conclude that probable problems of technical character and imperfect control system of training results are characterized by the critical level of safety. The lack of skills of self-organization in the process of distance learning is in the precritical condition. As for the other risks – they are in the unstable condition.

3. The complex of actions for increase of efficiency of distance learning of specialists in tourism in higher educational institutions based on the pedagogical technology is proposed. The given technology means dependence of quality of knowledge of students of distance learning on the level of motivational program and pedagogical communications.

The offered economic mechanism will allow reducing the risks of distance learning of specialists in tourism in higher educational institutions and, accordingly, providing the development of territories.

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